

Smoothing Outlier Scores Is All You Need to Improve Outlier Detectors (Extended Abstract)

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Abstract—Existing outlier detectors calculate outlier scores for data objects independently, ignoring the consistency between score similarity and object similarity. As a result, these detectors may produce inconsistent scores for similar objects, leading the scores of some normal objects to exceed some of outlier objects, increasing the possibility of misclassification. To address this issue, we first assume that *similar objects should have similar scores*. Then, based on this assumption, we propose neighborhood averaging, an outlier score post-processing technique to improve any single outlier detector, which is the first of its kind.

Index Terms—Anomaly detection, neighborhood averaging, NA, outlier detection.

I. INTRODUCTION

An outlier is an object that deviates significantly from other objects. Outlier detection plays a vital role in computer science as it has important applications such as fraud detection and fault detection. Therefore, large Internet companies including Google Cloud and Amazon Cloud have integrated outlier detection technology to their cloud computing services.

Throughout the years, numerous outlier detectors utilizing both deep learning (DL) and non-DL methods have been developed. Nonetheless, these detectors typically compute the outlier scores for individual objects in isolation, failing to account for the relationship between score similarity and object similarity. Consequently, they do not ensure the generation of consistent scores for similar objects. This inconsistency may lead to significantly divergent scores for similar objects, which can result in the scores of certain normal objects surpassing those of some outlier objects, thereby heightening the risk of misclassification. Fig. 1 illustrates such an example with the local outlier factor (LOF) detector [2], where the inconsistent scores of neighboring (i.e. similar) outlier objects cause some of these outlier objects to have lower scores than some normal objects located at the cluster boundaries, resulting in some of these normal objects being incorrectly identified as outliers (cross). This shows that the issue of inconsistent scores cannot be ignored.

To solve this score inconsistency issue, we first assume that *similar objects should have similar scores* which is applicable to outlier scores generated by any outlier detector. Then, following this assumption, we developed a score post-processing method called neighborhood averaging (NA) to enhance any single outlier detector.

This extended abstract is based on our recent paper [1] published in the IEEE TKDE journal. In [1], we (1) first highlighted the importance of outlier score smoothing for outlier detectors, (2) proposed the first score smoothing method suitable for any single detector (i.e., NA), and (3) presented theoretical and experimental analysis of NA. With this abstract, we would like to present a poster to increase the visibility of our work in light of existing and recent developments.

Fig. 1. Visualization of the outlier scores (Top row) and the detected outliers (Bottom row). The results at the left column and right column are given by the LOF detector [2] with and without NA, respectively ($k = 40$). LOF falsely detects boundary objects as outliers (cross) as evaluated on a 2-dimensional dataset, while NA improves the result of the LOF significantly.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Outlier Detectors

Outlier detection methodologies can be classified into two main categories based on the application of DL. Non-DL methods such as [2] are generally recognized for their high interpretability; however, they frequently struggle with the analysis of complex structured data. Conversely, while DL methods are adept at handling such data, they are often criticized for their lack of interpretability. A significant limitation that both DL-based and non-DL-based detection approaches share is their propensity to calculate outlier scores for individual objects

in isolation, which results in a disregard for the consistency between score similarity and object similarity.

B. Techniques to Enhance Outlier Detectors

Several techniques have been developed to improve the performance of outlier detectors. The most typical technique is outlier ensemble which improves the performance of outlier detection by leveraging the results of multiple outlier detectors. The pros and cons of different ensembles can be found in [3]. However, ensemble is not suitable for improving a single detector. To improve a single detector, in our previous work [4], a data preprocessing method called neighborhood representative (NR) was proposed. NR is an unbalanced sampling method used to increase the difference between groups containing different numbers of objects, which can increase the score gap between normal and outlier objects. However, NR also does not consider the consistency between score similarity and object similarity.

III. NEIGHBORHOOD AVERAGING (NA)

The proposed NA cannot be used as a standalone detector to produce raw outlier scores, but can be used as an add-on component to any score-based outlier detector to enhance its performance by modifying its scores. NA updates the outlier score of an object by averaging its score and the scores of its neighbors. Given an object and its outlier score, NA works in two steps. First, it finds the k nearest neighbors (k -NN) of the given object. Second, it uses the average of its score and the scores of its k -NN as the revised score for this given object. Algorithm 1 shows the pseudocode of NA. Fig. 1 shows a visualization example of detecting outliers with and without NA. We can see that the LOF detector incorrectly detects many objects located at the cluster boundaries as outliers, but succeeds with NA.

Algorithm 1 NA($\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{s}, k$)

Input : Dataset \mathbf{X} , Raw outlier scores \mathbf{s} , Neighborhood size k
Output: Revised outlier scores $\boldsymbol{\theta}$
foreach $\mathbf{X}_i \in \mathbf{X}$ **do**
 | $\theta_i = \frac{1}{k+1}(\mathbf{s}_i + \sum_j \mathbf{s}_j)$, where \mathbf{X}_j is k -NN of \mathbf{X}_i
end

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

To verify the effectiveness of NA, we have tested NA with 12 baseline detectors based on both DL and non-DL on nine real-world datasets in the full version [1]. The outlier detection performance was measured mainly by the area under the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve (AUC). Below we briefly present key experimental results and show how NA [1], NR [4], and their combination improve LOF on three real-world datasets. More experimental results and detailed analysis can be found in the full version [1].

The experimental findings in [1] indicate that the application of NA enhances the performance of all twelve baseline detectors by an average of 13% relative to their original results (from 0.70 to 0.79 AUC) across nine real-world datasets. Moreover, DL-based detectors and even outlier detectors that

Fig. 2. Experiment results of LOF, NR+LOF, LOF+NA, and NR+LOF+NA on three real-world datasets *Parkinson*, *HeartDisease*, and *Spambase* ranging k . NA is significantly complementary to NR.

are already based on k -NN are also improved. Notably, the experimental results also demonstrate that a detector with initially subpar performance, when combined with NA, can surpass the performance of a detector that originally exhibited strong results (irrespective of its joint usage with NA). This finding implies that the detectors with poor performance assessed in prior research may have been significantly undervalued.

Fig. 2 shows an experiment from [1] to investigate whether NA as a score post-processing method can further improve our previous work NR, a data preprocessing method to improve any single detector. NR is applied to the dataset before applying outlier detectors, while NA is applied to the outlier scores after applying outlier detectors. We can see that both NA and NR can significantly improve LOF, while the combination of NA and NR can further significantly enhance the performance over using NA or NR alone, indicating that NA and NR are significantly complementary.

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